

- modern border
- modern river course
- reconstructed shoreline (3rd mil. BC), after Jotheri 2016: Fig. 5.1
- marshes (3rd mil. BC), after Jotheri 2016: Fig. 5.1

- ancient name of the site (TAVO)**
- modern name of the site (TAVO)**
- geographical accuracy being tentative/unknown
- modern city (DGM)

